

COVID-19 Impacts on Local Coffee Shops in Biñan City, Laguna: The Basis for Recovery Plan

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Abstract: Coffee shops are trendy for all ages, especially among millennials and Generation Z. They consider coffee shops as a getaway from home, work, and school. The popularity of coffee shops continuously rises because coffee drinking and socialization are part of Filipino culture. Hence, the birth of coffee shops is no surprise in every corner of main thoroughfares in the Philippines, especially in Biñan City, Laguna, known as the “City of Life”. However, the coffee shop businesses in Biñan City were greatly affected by the coronavirus pandemic which started in March 2020. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of Covid-19 impacts on the operations of local coffee shops in Binan City, Laguna, Philippines and how they were able to cope with the ongoing pandemic. The researchers used the convenience purposive sampling method in selecting the participants and a structured survey questionnaire to gather data and responses to answer the research questions. Weighted mean and percentage methods were utilized to interpret the results using the 3-point Likert scale. One-way Anova or F-test determined the significant differences in the responses between the three groups of participants with a result of. The general findings reject the hypothesis of having no significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents— (20) baristas and (10) coffee shop managers with regards to the level of impact of Covid 19 on the operations of selected coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna, Philippines.

Keywords: covid-19 pandemic, coffee shops, coffee shop managers, baristas, inventory of supplies, service procedures, sanitation procedures, sales performance, and human resource.

1. INTRODUCTION

Coffee shops are one of the most known types of restaurants in the market. According to Doordash for Merchants (2020), coffee shops belong to the top five popular most loved types of restaurants that customers cannot get enough of. It is defined as a beverage-focused establishment that offers coffee, tea, and a smaller menu of food or snacks. It typically offers counter service and prices are low to moderate (McCarthy, 2020). Based on the study conducted by Businesswire regarding market analysis, trends, and forecast of coffee shops, the market worldwide in the year 2019-2025 was projected to grow by US\$ 58.7 billion, driven by a compounded growth of 4.1%, as this also displays the potential to grow at over 4.6% over the years (Woods, 2019). According to the study made by Mordor Intelligence, since the global pandemic started in the year 2019 the market size of the global coffee market decreased and the main coffee importing consuming markets in Europe, North

America, and Asia are in the middle of the COVID-19 crisis and expected to rise on the year 2021-2026 and about 4.28% according to Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR.)

Based on the study made by Esquire, the Philippines is 5th of the biggest consumers of coffee globally and imports tons of coffee beans around the globe (Agujo, 2019). Coffee has been entrenched in Philippine Culture and plays a vital role in every Filipino family. According to the study of Kantar World Panel Philippines (2018), Filipinos shifted from moderate to heavy drinkers of coffee. That is the reason behind numerous sprouting coffee shops not just in Metro Manila but in the whole nation (Marinduque News, 2019). Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) stated that there are nearly 276,000 coffee farms in the country, with about 79.4 million trees in the Philippines and at the year 2019. There are 3,250,000 bags of coffee beans consumed and by 2020 the total coffee consumed in the Philippines will be about 3.3 million 60 kg bags. This reflects a long-term increase in coffee consumption over the years.

However, in the year 2019 a coronavirus outbreak started in Wuhan City, Hubei, China. It is a respiratory ailment caused by a novel coronavirus wherein this virus kills some of the healthy cells of our body once the virus enters through droplets of saliva and close contact with the infected person (Whyte, 2021). The first case of covid 19 was identified on January 30, 2020, in Metro Manila and continuously spread nationwide that is why the government imposed a total lockdown and community quarantine since March 15, 2020.

When the community lockdown was implemented in the Philippines, a lot of food establishments were forced to close their operations for everyone's safety since the government was concerned about the rising numbers of coronavirus cases. For the first time in a long history, people experienced and saw how the international and independent businesses were closed. Hotels, restaurants, coffee houses, tea shops, and the travel sector were mandated to be closed to follow the government's strict guidelines.

The economy of the coffee industry is one of the most affected areas in food service according to World Coffee Portal (2021). Independent coffee shops are the ones that have a big possibility of failure. These coffee shops must work hard to survive and continue their business even if there is a pandemic to attain success. As stated by Guerra (2021), as the world transitions to a "New Normal" a lot of independent coffee shops slowly learned to adapt to the changes that the government was implying for them to continuously operate to comply with the strict guidelines, they offer to take away and deliveries that will contribute on their daily income.

The coffee shop businesses in Biñan City, Laguna are just a few of the industries affected by Covid 19 pandemic. Binan City is labeled as the "City of Life" and recognized as a trading and commerce center in the south. Some of the independent stores, not just coffee shops, were closed until the local government lifted the Enhance Community Quarantine (ECQ) into the General Community Quarantine (GCQ). According to the Business Permit and Licensing Office in Biñan City, Laguna, coffee shops are one of the trendiest businesses in the city. There are a total of 28 independent coffee shops currently operating as of May 2021 and 10 independent coffee shops are operating for more than 3 years as of today (Manabat, 2021).

In this light, the researchers' main objective is to determine the level of impacts of COVID-19 on the operations of independent coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna, and how the owners and managers managed to sustain their business in the market.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 shows the conceptual paradigm of the study which is the Input-Process-Output. The theoretical framework of the study is based on Bertalanffy's General Systems Theory. General systems theory first came to the consideration of the scientific community in the 1960s through the works of a scholar, Karl Ludvig von Bertalanffy. From its originators' point of view, the common framework hypothesis is not a hypothesis at all, but "a working theory, the most work of which is to supply a hypothetical demonstration for clarifying, anticipating, and controlling marvels". Frameworks hypothesis in its current shape offers components with related areas such as artificial intelligence and communication hypothesis, and, for a few scholars, has been extended to envelop the environmental approach to social work. Frameworks hypothesis accepts that the world is deliberate which frameworks can best be caught on by analyzing them as all-encompassing substances. The theory's wife, widespread standards that start with the person-in-environment center not as it permitted for, but propose, the incorporation of cross-cultural substance as stated by Greene (2017).

Input is the first box of the diagram. The input of the study includes the demographic profile of the respondents, and their evaluation of COVID-19 impacts in Biñan City, Laguna. The researchers gathered the current statistics of coffee shops operating in Binan City from the Business Permit and Licensing Office located in Biñan City Hall, Laguna to determine the sampling size of coffee shops that will be included in the study. There were two groups of target participants: (10) coffee shop managers and (20) baristas. The researchers requested their approval to participate in the study.

In Process, in the second box of the diagram, the researchers administered survey questionnaires to the said participants online instead of doing the survey face-to-face. This is a precaution that the researchers would not be infected with coronavirus since the researchers were not vaccinated yet. Their responses were collected online and the data collected and tabulated. Results are presented in tables and figures as well as interpreted using the Likert scale. The results determine the perceived level of covid-19 impact on the different aspects of the business operations of coffee shops in Biñan City. To test the hypothesis, a one-way analysis of variance was applied to determine if there are significant differences between and among the responses of the participants.

Lastly, in Output, the ultimate goal of this research was to develop a plan of actions that will help to fail coffee shop businesses in Biñan City, Laguna who are greatly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. This will be done based on the results drawn from the survey.

Feedbacks are linked back to the process and input as the implementation of the proposed plan of actions will generate the stakeholders' feedback on their performance amidst the coronavirus outbreak.

Statement of the Problem

The study focused on determining

the level of impacts of Covid-19 on the operations of selected coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna based on the perspective of two groups of respondents: coffee shop managers and baristas which can be used in developing a recovery plan that will benefit coffee shop businesses greatly affected by the coronavirus pandemic. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. age,
 - b. gender
 - c. educational attainment, and
 - d. job position
2. What is the level of impact of Covid-19 on the operations of the coffee shop in terms of:
 - a. inventory of supplies,
 - b. service procedures,
 - c. sanitation procedures,
 - d. sales performance, and
 - e. human resource;

3. Is there any significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents with regards to the level of impact of Covid-19 to the coffee shop operations?
4. Based on the results of the study, what plan of action can be proposed to improve the business performance of the coffee shop businesses in Binan City, Laguna amidst the coronavirus pandemic?

Statement of Hypothesis

To answer the research problems that were raised in this study, the test results examined the following hypotheses at a .05 level of significance:

Ho1: With 0.9822 as the highest level of significance, there is a significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents with regards to the level of impacts of the Covid19 pandemic on the operations of selected coffee shops in Binan City, Laguna

Ho2: With 0.0451 considered below standard level of significance. Results suggest that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents; baristas and café managers have the same perception on the impact of Covid 19 in their coffee shop operations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Coffee shops are a place where individuals go to enjoy coffee, as well as work and hang out with friends. These spaces are moreover among the worst affected by the spread of COVID-19, with numerous being constrained to shut their operations since the pandemic was first declared (Kanniah, 2020). As stated by Juan and Rosario (2020), coffee is deeply entrenched in our culture. The way people consumed coffee evolved through the years, the traditional way at the farm level to coffee in the hotels have evolved. Now there are many ways to make coffee from international to local coffees. And through the years we saw different kinds of the coffee line like espresso-based beverages, latte, and cappuccinos.

The study of www.verité.org (2020) stated that in a lot of countries, coffee workers are defined as essential workers who continued to work even if there is a COVID-19 pandemic. Since the pandemic started a year ago, the coffee industry is starting to feel the changes.

One thing that does not change during the pandemic is the love of people for coffee. During the pandemic, the sales of coffee started to go down because many coffee shops were forcibly closed due to the lockdown implemented by the national government in March 2020.

At the end of March, the pandemic had gotten worse and over a fifth of the world's population had been placed under lockdown. The whole country was put to Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) as a countermeasure to combat coronavirus outbreaks. During this period, only those businesses like groceries, wet and dry markets, and pharmacies that provide necessities were allowed to open. Coffee shops were not included on the list not until the government allowed restaurants and beverage shops to operate with no dining during the 3rd quarter of 2020. This resulted in many people working from home and others being furloughed. This has affected most people's daily coffee drinking habits. Compared to the past, many have visited one coffee shop they love daily, while others explored a new shop each week. But since there is a pandemic, both groups will no longer be able to do so. Many coffee shops have closed their doors in a matter of years, some in just months, due to the loss their businesses are suffering. But most of them did not close for good. Independent coffee shops have reopened and are now offering takeaway and deliveries (Kanniah, 2020).

Gradually, coffee shops in Biñan City found their footing to operate but with limited dining capacity based on the guidelines set by the national government when Laguna was put to General Community Quarantine status or GCQ, then to Modified General Community Quarantine or MGCQ. In June 2020, the Philippine government allowed limited operations of coffee shops and bars. The Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) on Emerging Infectious Diseases stated that there are strict guidelines to follow in different places. If the area is in ECQ or Enhanced Community Quarantine, 30 percent operational capacity provided in the venue is allowed to enter so that the customers can follow the physical distancing and the operations are strictly taken away only until 6 pm. For GCQ or General Community Quarantine, 50 percent of store capacity and dine-ins are allowed until 9 pm. These protocols were imposed to curtail the spread of COVID-19 (Esguerra,2020).

However, operations were affected again by the decision of the national government to put Laguna in ECQ status again because of the rapid increase of incidence of Covid-19 not only in Laguna but also in the National Capital Region (Cordero, 2021) Covid-19 continuously affects coffee shops worldwide. It has an impact on coffee consumption and places these independent coffee shops into a challenging position that will help them face a better tomorrow. One of the threats that these shops experienced is the decrease of dining consumers.

Therefore, the researchers conducted a study which focuses on the level of Covid-19 impacts on the business operations of coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna. The goal of the study is to determine how the business areas of the selected coffee shops in terms of supplies inventory, service procedures, sanitation procedures, sales performance, and employee morale were affected by the ongoing coronavirus pandemic. The results of the study will be useful in devising a plan of action that will improve the business performance of coffee shops amidst the coronavirus pandemic.

3. METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research design, the selection of the participants as well as the instrumentation and validation, data gathering procedures, and treatment and analysis of data.

Research Design

In this study, quantitative research design was applied. It is defined as the process of collecting data in numerical format Bandari (2021.) The study has similarities with the research of Joonho (2018) entitled "*Attributes of the coffee shop business related to customer satisfaction*" wherein the researcher used the quantitative research design to measure customer satisfaction towards coffee shops. However, the conducted research focused on measuring the level of impacts of COVID-19 to the coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna rather than determining customer satisfaction.

There was a study by Zou, P., Hou D., & Li., M. (2020) conducted at Guangdong Province, China with the title, "*The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on firms: a survey in Guangdong Province, China*" wherein the researchers measured the level of impact of the pandemic to the firms located at the area using survey questionnaires can measure and get the result from 524 firms as the respondents. As a result: (1) 48.7% of firms-maintained stability, and 35.1% experienced a halt in operation or faced closure; (2) Nearly 70–90% already exploit online commerce or are willing to do so, and also remote office work, and digital operations. (3) 46% believe that they will certainly incur losses for 2020, and 83.5% expect the city's GDP to decrease.

Table 1. 3-Point Likert Scale

Numbers	Mean Range	V.I Code	Verbal Interpretation
1	1.00-1.49	HA	Highly Affected
2	1.50-2.49	MA	Moderately Affected
3	2.50-3.00	SA	Slightly Affected

Table 1 shows the Likert scale used in determining and measuring the level of impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the business operations of coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna. 1-1.49 has a verbal interpretation of Slightly Affected (SA) while 1.50-2.49 has a verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected (MA), and lastly 2.50-3.00 with a verbal interpretation of Highly Affected (HA).

Research Locale

The researchers conducted the study in Biñan City, Laguna where different coffee shops were invited to participate. Coffee shops that had been operating for at least three (3) years were the target respondents. 10 coffee shop managers and 20 employed baristas were part of the study because they are experienced in terms of the challenges and changes in coffee shop operations during the pandemic.

The study was conducted from July to August 2021.

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were 20 coffee shop baristas and 10 coffee shop managers total of 30 respondents from local coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna that have been operating since 2018. The researchers selected coffee shop managers and baristas as respondents since they were very familiar with the effects of Covid-19 in their businesses. The researchers believe that they are qualified enough to answer the survey questionnaire.

The selected coffee shop managers and baristas had 3 - 4 years of working experience at the coffee shop they were working at validating the management experience in the coffee business industry and witnessed the impact of COVID-19 at their business.

Research Sampling

The researchers used the convenience purposive sampling method, which was used by Edgard and Manz (2017) in their study entitled "*Research Method for Cyber Security*" wherein it is the process where they collect samples that are conveniently located at the area of their study. The researchers adapted the sampling technique used in their study to obtain the range of answers and opinions lastly, to identify tentative hypotheses that can be used in rigorously further research. There were total of 30 respondents which consists of (20) coffee shop baristas and (10) coffee shop managers who participated to comply to the research sampling technique.

Research Instrument

The researchers used a survey questionnaire to gather information and answers to the questions raised in the study. The survey questionnaires were adapted from the study of Joonho (2018) entitled "*Attributes of the coffee shop business related to customer satisfaction*" wherein they measured the level of customer satisfaction using a survey questionnaire. In the first part of the survey, the demographic profile of the respondents was asked and in the second part, the Likert scale method was used to determine the level of impact of Covid 19 on coffee shops business operations. The said questionnaires were constructed by the researchers in two parts using Google Forms. The constructed questionnaires were checked by the adviser for approval. By receiving an approval, the survey questionnaires were administered to the respondents.

The first part of the survey questionnaire determined the respondents' demographic profile in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, job position, and years of experience.

The second part of the survey contains open-ended questions per category that the respondents should answer by elaborating their perception on the level of Covid 19 impact on their business operations guided by the 3-point Likert Scale. The respondents evaluated business operation areas affected by the Covid-19 pandemic which include Supplies Inventory, Service Procedures, Sanitation Procedures, Sales Performance, and Employee Morale.

Any company should have an excellent business operation that can attain success in the market because, without a good plan of operations management, there is a higher chance of conflict between each department that affected the whole firm resulting to low product quality and a chance for your competitors (Planet Together, 2021). Business operations should be planned to attain product quality, customer satisfaction, revenue increase, waste reduction, and a higher chance of collaboration or investments from other companies.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers gathered most of their related literature and studies from the internet, research papers, books, thesis papers, and from the Business Permit and Licensing Office in Biñan City, Laguna. The researchers selected coffee shops that are currently operating this year and have been operating for at least three (3) years.

Survey questionnaires were produced through Google Forms and distributed online to the selected 20 coffee shop managers and 20 baristas who voluntarily agreed and participated in the study. The researchers provided a Google Form link to the said respondents.

Data Treatment and Analysis

Data collected about the demographic profile were tabulated using the frequency method by percentage and the means to generate the total answers of the respondents. These were presented in tables and figures.

The means per dependent variable (business areas) were computed and interpreted using the 3-point Likert scale to determine the level of impact. The same data were analyzed statistically to determine the significant differences in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents. The researchers used ANOVA to determine differences in the means. The ANOVA test allows a comparison of more than two groups at the same time to determine whether a relationship exists between them (Kenton, 2021). In this study, the researchers used ANOVA to determine differences in the means.

In this way, the researchers can understand how different groups respond with the assumed null hypothesis, whether there is a connection or none.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the researchers show the gathered data result in figure, its analysis and interpretation; this includes the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, highest educational attainment, job status and work experience. This will also present the data results regarding the evaluation of two groups (barista and café manager) on the impact of Covid-19 on their business operations in terms of inventory of supplies, service procedures, sanitation procedures, sales performance, and human resource

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Figure 2. Age

Figure 2 illustrates the demographic profile of the respondents according to their age. The majority of the respondents are between 18-30 years old, corresponding to 66.7% of the total number of respondents while the minority are 41 years old and above, corresponding to only 6.7% of the total number of respondents.

This indicates that most of the hired workers in coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna are young adults with the age of 18-30 years old. Part time jobs are common in this kind of industry, but the onset of the pandemic greatly affected the rise of application from young adults.

According to UNHCR (2021), the rise of financial crises in the country as well as the drastic fall of employment and income rate brought by the pandemic has a devastating effect on people and their families. Thus, the majority of young adults, specifically students and fresh graduates are forced to find extra income to meet their basic needs.

Figure 3. Gender

Figure 3 shows the demographic profile of the respondents according to their gender, the majority of the respondents are male, corresponding to 66.7% of the total number of respondents. On the other hand, the least are female, corresponding to 33.3% of the total number of respondents.

It specifies that even if there are lots of women working in coffee shops, male baristas still represent the face of the coffee industry. There is a term called “manly coffee” which emphasizes the complexity of coffee making rather than providing customers entertainment where females have the best skills. Until today, there is still continual cultural discourse about the wide gender gap of workers in this kind of industry (Grozanick, 2015).

Figure 4. Highest Educational Attainment

Figure 4 displays the demographic profile of the respondents according to their highest educational attainment; the majority of the respondents are college/post graduate, corresponding to 46.7% of the total number of the respondents. The minority are high school/vocational course takers corresponding to 16.7% of the total number of respondents.

This data shows that most of the hired workers of local coffee shops are college/post graduates. Since the chosen respondents have specific job titles and years of experience; coffee shop managers and baristas, it is projected that most of them have post-grade credentials.

Coffee businesses prefer to seek employees with college diplomas to ensure they have in-depth knowledge on coffee. Based on an article titled “*What are the Main Benefits of Hiring Graduates?*”, it is advantageous for businesses to hire a student or fresh graduate for easier employee management and flexible job description. Though, it is better to hire someone who has undergone proper training and has sharpened the set of skills they need for coffee production and marketing endeavors.

Figure 5. Job Position

Figure 5 exhibits the demographic profile of the respondents according to their job position. The majority of the respondents are between baristas, corresponding to 66.7% of the total number of respondents while the minority are managers, corresponding to only 33.3% of the total number of respondents.

The data evidently imposes the preceding total number of respondents chosen by researchers in data gathering procedure. Staff in coffee shops usually requires one cafe manager and numerous baristas in-operation. Accordingly, there are a larger number of baristas (20) than the total number of cafe managers (10) as respondents of this study.

Figure 6. Years of Work Experience

Figure 6 reveals the demographic profile of the respondents according to their years of work experience, the majority of the respondents has 1-3 years, corresponding to 40% of the total number of respondents. On the other hand, the least has 7-10 years, corresponding to 13.3% of the total number of respondents.

This data points to the prior stated result that fresh graduates are the majority workers in local coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna. According to the article “*What are the Main Benefits of Hiring Graduates?*”, businesses prefer new job applicants over veterans for the sake of wanting lower salary cost and easier employee management.

Moreover, few years of work experience connects with cafe norms regarding part time jobs which are essential labor for workers whereas this benefits on expounding their professional experience for a higher job position.

2. The Level of Impact of Covid-19 on the Operations of the Coffee Shop in terms of Inventory of Supplies, Service Procedures, Sanitation Procedures, Sales Performance, and Human Resource.

Table 2 shows the evaluation result of the respondents regarding Inventory of Supplies. Questions 1 to 5 all got 2.13, 2.36, 2.16 and 2.0 respectively with verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected (MA).

Table 2. Inventory of Supplies

Questions	Mean	V.I
1. Selecting suppliers.	2.133	MA
2. Sourcing of available supplies in the area.	2.367	MA
3. Ordering of supplies.	2.167	MA
4. Performing physical and perpetual inventory of supplies.	2.000	MA
Overall Mean	2.167	MA

Among the 4 sub variables of inventory of supplies, the “sourcing of available supplies in the area” got the highest mean score of 2.367. This means that it was greatly affected by the pandemic in terms of importing supplies in coffee industry comparable to the data of Motor Intelligence (2019) wherein the study targets the international market.

Thus, the overall mean of respondent’s evaluation on Inventory of Supplies is 2.167 interpreted as Moderately Affected (MA) level of impact. Since the market size of global coffee market increased as the pandemic surge, it is evident that the main coffee importing market in Europe, North America and Asia expected to rise for about 4.26% according to Compound Annual Growth Rate (Mordor Intelligence, 2019). Meaning, the data result reflects the change of prices and quality when it comes on importing coffee shop supplies.

Table 3 shows the evaluation result of the respondents regarding Service Procedure. Questions 1 to 5 all got 2.0, 1.9, 2.1, 2.03 and 1.83 respectively with verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected (MA).

Table 3. Service Procedure

Questions	Mean	V.I
1. Response time in accepting orders of food and beverages (phone call and online).	2.000	MA
2. Providing quality service of food and beverages.	1.900	MA
3. Preparing orders of food and beverages (both dine-in and take-out).	2.100	MA
4. Time preparation of the food/drinks.	2.033	MA
5. Delivery of food and beverages to customers.	1.833	MA
Overall Mean	1.973	MA

Among the 4 sub variables of service procedure, the “time preparation of the food/drinks” got the highest mean score of 2.033. This indicates that like the data report of World Coffee Portal (2021), this sub variable was greatly affected by the pandemic unlike the others for the reason that making food and beverages are different when it comes to in-store dine and delivery.

The total mean of respondent’s evaluation on Service Procedure is 1.973 which corresponds to Moderately Affected (MA) level of impact. This corresponds to World Coffee Portal (2021) report that the economy of coffee industry is considered as one of the most affected areas of the pandemic in terms of food service. This enforced coffee shops to change their offer to take-away and delivery services to comply with the health protocols.

Table 4 shows the evaluation result of the respondents regarding Sanitation Procedure. Questions 1, 3, 4 got of 2.23, 2.16 and 2.03 respectively with verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected (MA).

Table 4. Sanitation Procedure

Questions	Mean	V.I
1. Cleaning and sanitizing the preparation area.	2.233	MA
2. Cleaning and sanitizing the customer service area.	2.267	HA
3. Waste management procedures of the coffee shop.	2.167	MA
4. Personal hygiene of manager and staff.	2.033	MA
Overall Mean	2.175	MA

Among the 4 sub variables of sanitation procedure, the “cleaning and sanitizing the customer service area” got the highest mean score of 2.267. The result means that it is the most affected by the pandemic corresponds to the study of Esguerra (2020) wherein establishment hygiene should be highly maintained in order to protect customers from health risks brought by Covid 19.

On the other hand, question number 3 had mean score of 2.26 interpreted as Highly Affected (HA). Overall, the respondent’s evaluation on Service Procedure is 2.175 which level of impact is Moderately Affected (MA). The result highly supports the health guidelines implemented by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) on Emerging Infectious Diseases regarding to the limited percent operational capacity provided in the venue for the customers to follow social distancing mainly to restrain the spread of COVID-19 (Esguerra, 2020).

Table 5 shows the result of evaluation of the respondents regarding Sales Performance. Questions 1 to 5 all got 2.20, 1.93, 1.9 and 2.13 respectively with verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected (MA).

Table 5. Sales Performance

Questions	Mean	V.I
1. Promoting food and drinks.	2.200	MA
2. Selling of hot and cold beverages (dine-in).	1.933	MA
3. Selling of snacks like sandwiches and pastries (dine-in).	1.900	MA
4. Quantity of take-outs and deliveries.	2.133	MA
Overall Mean	2.042	MA

Among the 4 sub variables of sales performance, “promoting food and drinks” got the highest mean score of 2.200. This indicates that it was greatly affected by the pandemic comparable to the study of Kanniah (2020) regarding to the disrupt shutdown of numerous coffee shops in Metro due to the early stage of pandemic lockdowns.

Hence, the overall mean of respondent’s evaluation on Sales Performance is 2.042 interpreted as Moderately Affected (MA) level of impact. This corresponds that during pandemic, the sales of coffee started to go down because many coffee shops were forcibly closed due to the lockdown implemented by the national government in and at the same time their rapidly change of service procedure (Kanniah, 2020).

Table 6 shows the evaluation result of the respondents regarding Human Resource. Questions 1 to 3 consistently got rounded mean of 2.0 verbally interpreted as Moderately Affected (MA).

Table 6. Human Resource

Questions	Mean	V.I
1. Hiring and scheduling of personnel.	2.000	MA
2. Salary and wage management including incentives and benefits.	2.000	MA
3. Monitoring of the social well-being of personnel.	2.000	MA
Overall Mean	2.000	MA

All sub variables of human resource equally got mean scores of 2.000. The data result suggests that unlike the other main variables, human resource was the least variable affected by the pandemic unlike the study of Verité Organization (2020) that claimed that Covid 19 highly affected coffee shops workers especially to their general acuity to their working environment.

The total mean of respondent’s evaluation on Human Resource is exactly 2.0 which corresponds to Moderately Affected (MA) level of impact. The result interprets similarly to the study in Verité Organization (2020) that coffee workers who continued to work in the midst of Covid 19 stated the inevitable change of their employee morale as their environment at work deliberately had new norms brought by the aforementioned pandemic.

Table 7 shows the total evaluation of respondents on Covid-19 impact to coffee shop operations in terms of the given variables. Inventory of Supplies, Service Procedure, Sanitation Procedure, Sales Performance, and Human Resource got mean scores of 2.167, 1.973, 2.175, 2.042 and 2.0 respectively with verbal interpretation of Moderately Affected (MA).

Table 7. Overall Evaluation of Variables

Variables	Mean	V.I
1. Inventory of Supplies	2.167	MA
2. Service Procedure	1.973	MA
3. Sanitation Procedure	2.175	MA
4. Sales Performance	2.042	MA
5. Human Resource	2.000	MA
Overall Mean	2.071	MA

Among the 5 variables, “sanitation procedure” got the highest mean score of 2.175 which indicates that it was greatly affected by the pandemic. In place of the overall mean of respondent’s evaluation, table 7 shows 2.071 which corresponds that Covid-19 pandemic **Moderately Affected** business operations of local coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna.

The data result similarly corresponds to the general study of World Coffee Portal (2021) which stated that the economy of the coffee industry is one of the most affected areas in food and beverages by the surge of Covid 19 pandemic worldwide.

3. Significant Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents with Regards to the Level of Impact of Covid-19 to the Coffee Shop Operations.

Table 8 shows that inventory of supplies has the highest level of significance with 0.4714 while sales performance is considered to be lowest with 0.0720. Result suggests that there’s no significant difference of evaluation when grouped according to age and gender.

Table 8. t-test (Age and Gender)

In dependent Samples T-test	Statistics		p
Inventory of Supplies	Mann-Whitney U	83.500	0.4714
Service Procedure	Mann-Whitney U	72.000	0.2096
Sanitation Procedure	Mann-Whitney U	77.000	0.3162
Sales Performance	Mann-Whitney U	60.000	0.072
Human Resource	Mann-Whitney U	64.000	0.1073

This favors the hypothesis of having no significant difference in evaluation of the two groups of respondents with regards to the level of impacts of the Covid 19 on the operations of selected coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna.

Table 9 displays that sanitation procedure has the highest level with 0.9822 while sales performance has below standard level of significance with 0.0451. Results suggest that there is a significant difference only for sales performance when grouped according to job position.

Table 9. t-test (Job Position)

In dependent Samples T-test	Statistics		p
Inventory of Supplies	Mann-Whitney U	73.500	0.2419
Service Procedure	Mann-Whitney U	95.000	0.8373
Sanitation Procedure	Mann-Whitney U	99.000	0.9822
Sales Performance	Mann-Whitney U	55.500	0.0451
Human Resource	Mann-Whitney U	60.500	0.0768

This nulls the hypothesis of having no significant difference in evaluation which specifies that both groups of respondents; baristas and café managers have the same perception on the impact of Covid 19 in their coffee shop operations.

Table 10 exemplifies that sanitation procedure has the highest level with 0.9476 while supplies inventory has below standard level of significance with only 0.0310.

Table 10. ANOVA (Age)

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric)	χ^2	df	p
Inventory of Supplies	6.948	2	0.031
Service Procedure	1.685	2	0.4307
Sanitation Procedure	0.108	2	0.9476
Sales Performance	2.976	2	0.2258
Human Resource	1.887	2	0.3893

Even though this only links to the sole group of demographic characteristics of respondents, this data contrasts the suggesting result of independent sample t-test according to both age and gender. Results suggest significant differences only for supplies inventory when grouped according to age.

Table 11 illustrates that service procedure has the highest level with 0.8458. On the other hand, human resources correspond to 0.0113 and sales performance has 0.0213 levels of significance. Both measured below the standard level of significance which is 0.05. Results suggest significant differences for human resource and sales performance when grouped according to educational attainment.

Table 11. ANOVA (Educational Attainment)

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric)	χ^2	df	p
Inventory of Supplies	0.885	2	0.6426
Service Procedure	0.335	2	0.8458
Sanitation Procedure	0.565	2	0.7539
Sales Performance	7.695	2	0.0213
Human Resource	8.968	2	0.0113

The data shows that human resource and sales performance were correspondingly perceived to be affected by the pandemic by respondents regardless of their educational attainment. This varies the result of preceding grouped tests in accordance to other demographic characteristics of respondents as it has more than one below standard level of significance.

Table 12 also indicates that service procedure got the highest level with 0.8052. human resource only has the least level of significance with 0.0037. Results suggest significant differences only for supplies inventory when grouped according to work experience.

Table 12. ANOVA (Work Experience)

One-Way ANOVA (Non-parametric)	χ^2	df	p
Inventory of Supplies	4.739	3	0.1920
Service Procedure	0.984	3	0.8052
Sanitation Procedure	1.567	3	0.6670
Sales Performance	4.949	3	0.1756
Human Resource	13.47	3	0.0037

The general findings reject the hypothesis of having no significant difference in evaluation of the two groups of respondents— barista and coffee shop managers with regards to the level of impact of the Covid 19 on the operations of selected coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna.

5. CONCLUSION

This section shows the summary findings and aims to disclose suitable answers towards the statement of the problem.

Inventory of Supplies

The data result confirms that Covid 19 **moderately affected (MA)** coffee shop business operations in Biñan City, Laguna when it comes to their supply inventories. Regardless of age and years of work experience, café employees clearly distinguished the impact of pandemic in terms on how they run their raw materials— their struggles of selecting new suppliers, sourcing available supplies in the area and articulating quantity of take outs and deliveries.

Service Procedures

The result settles that service procedures of local coffee shops in Biñan, Laguna are **moderately affected (MA)** by the pandemic surge. The change in customer habits of staying-at-home makes coffee shops take more delivery orders than standard dining services. The time preparation and quality of serving food and beverages of the two premises are different. Meaning, coffee shops opt for altering their service procedures to comply for transport purposes.

Sanitation Procedures

The data result exhibits that Covid 19 **moderately affected (MA)** sanitation procedures of coffee shops in Biñan, Laguna. Since there are health risks brought by the pandemic, health protocols are crucial in food and beverages industry because their main priority is health security of consumers. Thus, it is expected that cleaning and sanitizing customer's area are very particular to café staff as its level of impact result shows **highly affected (HA)** by the pandemic.

Sales Performance

The result submits that sales performance of Biñan City, Laguna's coffee shops are **moderately affected (MA)** by Covid 19 according to the respondents' evaluation. This implies the perception of café employees (baristas and coffee shops managers) with regards on how they promote their food and beverage products to customers in a pandemic situation.

Human Resources

Human resources also have **moderately affected (MA)** level of impact for the reason that Covid 19 affected coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna when it comes on their personnel; having hiring process of new employees, measuring salary and wage management including incentives and benefits of current shop working in the middle of pandemic crisis.

6. RECOMMENDATION

In this section, researchers propose a plan of actions to improve the business performance of selected coffee shops in Binan City, Laguna amidst the coronavirus pandemic. Suggestions are based on the level of impact result of the study.

Inventory of Supplies

Performing physical and perpetual supply inventory is one of the aspects of inventory of supplies on the coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna. This has been the most severely impacted aspect. Researchers suggest coffee shops should invest more in advanced technological systems such as Point of Sale (POS) systems and scanners to help them manage their supply inventory easier and with more conveniency.

Service Procedures

According to the findings, the most impacted aspect of service procedure of local coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna is providing quality food and beverage service. Researchers suggests that coffee shops should participate their employees in receiving proper training on both dining and delivery service to ensure that their personnel have flexible skill and can provide quality service to their customers in any circumstances.

Sanitation Procedures

Aside from thoroughly cleaning and sanitizing customer's area, researchers suggest personal hygiene of café personnel as one of the most affected aspects in the sanitation procedure at coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna. Employees of coffee shops should practice good personal hygiene to prevent the virus from spreading.

Employees should also understand how to properly wash their hands to avoid food contamination. Sanitation is critical not only because we are in the midst of a pandemic, but also to ensure the safety and health of the customers.

Sales Performance

According to the findings, Covid-19 had a major impact on the majority of coffee shops' sales performance in Biñan City, Laguna, in terms of promoting food and beverage to customers. To solve this problem, researchers recommend coffee shops to advertise on different social media platforms and show customers the security precautions they take in their establishments so that customers feel safe while dining.

They must also ensure that there is outside dining so that guests can choose whether to eat inside or outside. In addition, Coffee shops should choose good quality ingredients and high-quality equipment to make their products to make sure that they will provide good quality products to their customers.

Human Resource

Based on data results, the hiring and scheduling of personnel is the most affected in terms of human resources of the coffee shops in Biñan City, Laguna. To ensure everyone's safety, the researchers recommend that they have a weekly rapid test, COVID-19 vaccines, no signs of the virus, and fill out a health declaration form on a daily basis.

Following these guidelines will ensure that all coffee shop employees can come to work and that personnel work schedule is not disrupted. In terms of hiring, coffee shops should educate new employees on the new normal protocol so that they are aware of what they must do once they require to enter their working environment.

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